

FABRICATION AND MECHANICAL TESTING OF SLAG REINFORCED ALUMINUM METAL MATRIX

KATHIRAVAN S¹, MANIVEL C², SIVALAKSHMI S³, RAJA M³, PRAKASH P⁴
THANIGAIVELAN R^{5,*},

¹Alpha College of Engineering, Chennai, India-600124

²NPR College of Engineering and Technology, Natham, Dindigul, India-624401

³Government College of Engineering, Salem-636011

⁴K.S.Rangasamy College of Technology, Tiruchengode, India- 637215

⁵Shreenivasa Engineering College, Dharmapuri, India-635301

*Email:tvelan10@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: In this study, metal matrix composite (MMC) materials were made with an aluminum matrix (AA6061 alloy) and reinforcement Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS) elements using molten metal stir casting. The fabricated composite samples were subjected to mechanical testing of Al6061/GGBS composite samples with varying composition of GGBS such as i) 2.5 wt.%, ii) 5 wt.% and iii) 7.5 wt.%. The mechanical testing showed that the mechanical characteristics enhanced with the increase in GGBS reinforcement. The Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite attained the maximum enhancement in properties. Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite's Brinell hardness improved to 110 BHN, Ultimate Tensile strength improved to 210 MPa and Wear rate (Load 2 Kg.) decreased to 105 micrometer compared to unreinforced Al6061specimen. Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite's impact strength (Charpy) decreased to 7.9 Joule compared to Al6061specimen's 15 J.

KEYWORDS: Blast Furnace Slag, metal matrix composites, Hardness, Wear, Tensile

1 INTRODUCTION

The applicability of metal matrix composites (MMCs), that too particularly aluminium metal matrix composites (AMMCs) are widely researched in all kinds of manufacturing industries to reduce weight, without compromising on properties that would benefit both technically and economically. In 2023, Kannan et al. created hybrid nano-MMCs based on aluminum and investigated how temperature, sliding load, and sliding velocity affected the wear behavior of a new hybrid metal matrix nano-composite. According to the results of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), sliding load has the greatest influence (62.33%), whereas

strength than other composites, as well as lower porosity and metal loss (wear). Using a stir casting technique, Mythili et al. (2025) created AMMCs from Al6061 alloy reinforced with varying weight percentages of Al₂O₃, such as 6% and 8%. The prepared AMMCs specimen is subjected to tensile, compressive, wear, and hardness testing in compliance with ASTM guidelines. Tensile strength is 129 N/mm² and 140 N/mm², compressive strength is 384 N/mm² and 419 N/mm², coefficient of friction is 0.22 and 0.37, and hardness is 51.72 HV and 52.86

reinforcement accounts for 19.40%. Using scrap aluminum alloy wheels (SAAWs) with 1, 2, and 3 weight percent of nanosized alumina ((Al₂O₃)_n) particles and 4, 5.5, and 7 weight percent of microsized alumina ((Al₂O₃)_m) particles as reinforcing components, Thiraviam et al.(2020) created aluminum– Al₂O₃ hybrid metal matrix composites. To ascertain the impact of nano- and micro-sized alumina on wear behavior, pin-on-disc wear tests were carried out under uniform load conditions in a dry environment. With an amplitude of 100% and a pulse on-time of 180s, the results showed that SAAWs reinforced with 1 weight percent of nanosized alumina particles and 5.5 weight percent of microsized Al₂O₃ particles had higher hardness, tensile strength, and compressive HV for the 6% and 8% reinforced AMMCs. The mechanical properties of Al6061/Ni and Al6061/Cr MMCs with different weight percentages of Ni and Cr were examined by Beldar&Kumavat (2024). ASTM D 3552 is used for tensile testing; ASTM D790 is used for flexural strength evaluation; ASTM E384 is used for microhardness evaluation; and ASTM D256 is used for impact strength evaluation. All things considered, Al6061/Ni MMCs perform better mechanically than Al6061/Cr MMCs, with the latter showing superior elongation, flexural strength,

and impact strength. This study demonstrates that the Al6061 alloy undergoes structural changes that improve its mechanical qualities when nickel and chromium are added. For possible ballistic applications, Rahman et al. (2024) created and examined an aluminum nickel phosphorus bronze (AlNPB) MMC reinforced with synthetic TiCN + SiCnanopowders. Tensile, compression, and hardness tests, as well as mechanical performance, revealed that 4 weight percent reinforcement produced the best results, with a tensile strength of 753 MPa, a hardness of 448 HBW, and a compression strength of 77.9 J. Additionally, corrosion resistance was good. Additionally, a ballistic examination of the MMC showed that, in comparison to the 2% and 6% TiCN + SiC nanoparticle-reinforced aluminum bronze matrix composites, there was less residual strain energy following bullet impact on a 4 weight percent reinforcement target plate. Accordingly, this analysis indicates that the most promising balance of mechanical properties for ballistic applications is provided by an AlNPB MMC with 4 weight percent reinforcement. In their research, Ahmad et al. (2024) investigated the creation and characterisation of stir-cast Al-7075/TiO₂ MMCs with TiO₂ concentrations ranging from 2% to 10%. The material is suitable for important wear and tribology applications, as evidenced by the incremental improvements in Martens, Elastic Indentation, and Vickers Hardness shown in hardness assessments. Particularly with 8% TiO₂, the composites showed improved damping flexural properties. For 8% TiO₂ mix MMC, the stated maximum and minimum modulus values are 98.9 GPa at 25 °C and 77.3 GPa at 350 °C. Reduced wear rates and COF values enhanced tribological performance. It is evident from the discussed literatures, the fabrication and mechanical characteristics testing was performed worldwide and, in this research, Al6061 material is considered as prominent composition for fabricating the MMCs along with Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBFS). The fabrication of Al6061/GGBFS is done through stir-casting method which is a simple and economical process and also the industrial waste, GGBS recycled in the form of reinforcement would be environmentally beneficial. The fabricated composite samples were subjected to mechanical testing of Al6061/GGBS composite samples with varying composition of GGBS such as i) 2.5 wt.%, ii) 5 wt.% and iii) 7.5 wt.%.

2 MATERIALS USED FOR MMC FABRICATION

The choices of materials available for utilizing matrix as well as reinforcement are numerous. Hence

researchers are keen to explore solid industrial wastes as reinforcement materials as they contain mostly ceramic compounds and can be good resources for making MMCs. Thus, selection of least explored materials would pave way for new genre of MMCs. Al6061, a versatile and widely used aluminum cast alloy, is known for its excellent mechanical properties and good weldability. It features a balanced composition of magnesium and silicon, which provides moderate to high strength while maintaining good corrosion resistance. This alloy is heat-treatable, allowing for various temper conditions that can enhance its properties for specific applications. Al6061 is commonly used in aero, auto, and marine industries due to its lightweight nature and excellent machinability. It also performs well in structural applications, including frames and pipelines. Additionally, Al6061 is identified for its good surface finish and anodizing capabilities, making it suitable for aesthetic applications. Its balanced characteristics make it a popular choice for numerous engineering applications. Its chemical composition, physical properties and mechanical characteristics are given in tables 1 to 3 respectively.

Table 1. Al6061-Chemical Composition

Element	Si	Cu	Cr	Mg	Mn	Zn	Ti	Fe	Al
wt%	0.4-0.8	0.15-0.40	0.35	0.8-1.2	0.15	0.25	0.15	0.7	Remaining

Table 2. Al6061-Physical properties

Sl.No	Properties	Unit
1	Density	2.7g/cm ³
2	Melting point	588°C

Table 3. Mechanical properties of Al6061 in as-cast condition

Sl.No	Properties	Unit
1	Tensile strength	120-160MPa
2	Yield strength	70-110MPa
3	Elastic modulus	68.9GPa
4	Poisson's-ratio	0.33
5	Elongation	2-6%
6	Hardness(Brinell)	35-55

2.1 GGBS – The Reinforcement Material

GGBS is obtained from steel industries as by-product in molten state during the production of iron using the blast furnace where coke, limestone and other materials are added with iron-ore to reduce it to iron at about 15000C. It is a cementitious material (having binding and hardening characteristics like cement) mostly mixed with concrete as an alternative to cement. As it is a mixture of many ceramic compounds and due to the inherent characteristics of ceramics, it has the ability to enhance mechanical properties, thermodynamic stability and corrosion-resistance of aluminium composites when added as reinforcement material. The melting temperature of GGBS is about 15000 C and hence it is thermally stable and do not react with aluminium during fabrication. Figure 1 shows the particles of GGBS. It was witnessed from the literature review that only a very few have attempted to produce AMC with GGBS as reinforcement material. Hence this research has utilized GGBS to fabricate AMC samples to investigate its potential to enhance the composite's final properties and machinability. The composition of GGBS chemically is listed in Table 3.4 and the physical properties are itemized in table 5.

Fig.1 GGBS Particles for Reinforcement

2.2 Al6061/GGBS composite fabrication through Stir-casting

Generally, various manufacturing methods are available for producing the MMCs such as stir casting, squeeze casting, powder metallurgy and spray deposition. Among them stir casting is regarded as the most economical and simple method that yields very good results if properly executed (Ansar Kareem et al., 2021). Hence stir-casting was employed to produce Al6061/GGBS composite samples.

Steps involved in the process:

The steps that comprise the stir-casting process of Al6061/GGBS composite samples are detailed below.

Cleaning the materials: The Al6061 rods (diameter: 25 mm) were immersed in Sodium Hydroxide solution (10% concentration, at 1000C, for 10 - 15 minutes) and after removal cleaned by the solution of methanol. Similarly the GGBS particles (particle size around 20 μm) are preheated in a furnace to 6500C for removing contaminations, gases or volatile matters that may lead to clustering of the particles that would improve bonding tendency between matrix and reinforcement at interface. The preheating furnace was a separate one and its specifications are - Carbolite make STF 10/75; 3 Ph; 50 Hz; 6 kW; 2x 400 V; operating temp. up to 16000C.

Measure to reduce defects: Argon gas was passed into the slurry as an oxidation prevention measure (provides inert atmosphere) for reducing slag-formation and also avert the formation of pores, voids etc.

Melting in furnace to produce composite slurry: The required quantity of Al6061 was weighed and kept in a graphite crucible (with WOLFRAKOT coating inside) which is placed in an electric furnace (Power: 3 Ph; 50 Hz; 5kW, 440 V & max. temp. 11000C) and heated to 9000C. The preheated GGBS particles were weighed to the

Table 4. Chemical Composition of GGBS

Element	CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	K ₂ O	Fe ₂ O ₃	Na ₂ O
%wt	33.2	34.4	21.5	9.5	0.47	0.39	0.2	0.34

Table 5. The physical properties of GGBS

Characteristics	Description
Particle Size	Normally < 45 micrometers
Specific Surface Area	400 to 600 m ² /kg
Specific Gravity	2.9 to 3.0
Density	1.0 to 1.2 g/cm ³
Melting temperature	Around 15000C

required quantity and added to the melt gradually at a regular feed interval. The molten material's temperature was measured using a thermocouple kept in the crucible for this purpose. A stirring unit (mild steel blades + rod) is also fixed with the furnace for mixing. The composite slurry was thoroughly mixed at 400 rpm by the stirrer for every 5 minutes even after the addition of particles were over to get homogeneous mixture. The composite slurry then get poured down into pre-heated mould plates and kept there for some time to get solidified and then removed and placed in atmospheric conditions to attain normal room temperature. Al6061 composite with 2.5wt. %, 5wt. % 7.5wt. % GGBS samples and an unreinforced Al6061 sample were produced in this method. Figure 2 shows the stir-casting setup and process. The Al6061/GGBS samples produced with varied quantity of GGBS particles. The specimens were cut into required dimensions utilizing wire-cut electro-discharge machining and other machining processes to carry out mechanical and wear tests. Figures 3 and 4 show the specimens prepared for testing.

Fig.2 Stir-casting setup and fabrication process

Fig.3 Specimens fabricated through Stir-casting process

Fig. 4 Composite samples with different Percentage of GGBS reinforcement

3 MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF AL6061/GGBS COMPOSITES

3.1 Hardness Testing

Hardness tests have been carried out on all the four samples which include unreinforced Al6061 sample and the samples reinforced with 2.5wt%, 5wt% and 7.5wt% GGBS. The Brinell hardness test machine is used for the purpose. Brinell hardness tests were done on the specimens to evaluate the hardness. The process included making an impression on the surface using a 10 mm ball indenter with a load setting of 60 Kgf applied on the specimen about 30 seconds. After removing the load from the work piece, the impression was tested by using microscope. The measurements were taken at 3 different points on all sample work pieces and the averages were taken as the final values. The Brinell hardness is calculated as per Equation 1. ASTM standards were followed in preparing test specimens.

$$HB = \frac{2P}{\pi D(D - \sqrt{D^2 - d^2})} \quad (1)$$

Where,

HB – Brinell Hareness Number(kgf/mm²),

P- Applied Force (kgf),

D–Indenterdiameter(mm),

d–Indentationdiameter(mm),

The hardness values obtained for the samples are plotted in Figure 5. It is apparent that hardness value raises with the increase in GGBS Wt % (Manoj Kumar et al., 2020; Rao et al 2022).The cause is the inherent hardness of GGBS ceramic imparted to the composite. The Brinell hardness values produced by the composites are: Al6061: 64 BHN, 81 BHN, 94 BHN and 105 BHN respectively for unreinforced, 2.5 wt.%, 5 wt.% and 7.5wt.% reinforced composites. It can be noted that Al 6061 + 7.5 % GGBS provides the highest hardness value among the tested samples. (Ayyar and Chawla, 2007)

Fig.5 Hardness Test Results

3.2 Tensile Test

The tensile test is the one of the simplest and most widely used mechanical test for ductile materials. During a tensile test, the specimen pass over the elastic zone (yield point), plastic zone (deformation, elongation) of the material till failure occurs. The reinforced ceramic materials imparts hardness to the MMCs which simultaneously increases the tensile strength [10-12]. The level of increment of tensile strength imparted into MMCs for different percentages of reinforcement inclusion is evaluated through tensile tests. Tensile test was done in the computer based 'Universal Testing Machine'. Three test specimens were prepared for each volume fraction of GGBS particles inclusion and tested. The average value of the three test specimens for each composition was recorded. ASTM E8/E8M standards were adhered in the test specimen preparation.

Fig. 6 Tensile Test Sample

The figure 6, gives the geometry and dimensions of tensile specimens for the test. Test was performed at a strain-rate of 1mm/min and the 'ultimate tensile strength' was obtained for each specimen. It was found that the addition of GGBS particle in the AMCs has significantly increased the tensile property. The tensile strength values produced by the composites are: Al6061: 130 MPa, 162 MPa, 184 MPa and 210 MPa respectively for unreinforced, 2.5 wt.%, 5 wt.% and 7.5wt.% reinforced composites. It can be noted that AMC with 7.5wt.% GGBS reveals the maximum tensile strength. (Ayyar and Chawla, 2007)

Figure 7 shows the tensile test specimens used for tensile tests before (fresh specimens) and after the tests (broken specimens).

Fig. 7 Tensile specimens (a) Before Testing & (b) After testing

3.3 Impact Test

Impact tests are important for materials that are subjected to impact (sudden application) loads such as machine members sliding, colliding with one another, punching work etc. Attempts are also being made to use aluminium metal composite in such applications, it becomes necessary to conduct impact tests on them. As Charpy impact test is performed on ductile materials and AMCs contain ductile materials for the most part, and hence this test is carried out. The impact test (Charpy) was carried out using a specimen as per the standards of ASTM E23 (10 mm², 55 mm long with a notch of 2 mm depth for 45° and having 0.25 mm radius at the tip) and presented in figure 8. Since the impact strength is related to ductile property, the value decreases as the wt.% inclusion of GGBS increases [13-14]. The Charpy impact energy values obtained for 0 wt.%, 2.5 wt.%, 5 wt.% and 7.5 wt.% respectively are 15 J, 13 J, 9.8 J and 7.4 J. It is due to the decreasing proportion of the ductile Al6061 alloy and the increased addition of hard GGBS ceramic particles. As the hardness increases, the impact strength decreases.

Fig. 8 Impact Test Results

3.4 Wear Test

For identifying the wear characteristics of the Al6061/GGBS composites, the wear test is performed by a 'Pin on disc' machine. The wear test specimens were made with dimensions of 8 mm diameter and 30 mm height based on ASTM G 99 standard [15-17]. The test specimens were cleaned using ultrasonic cleaning machine and ethanol solution to make it free from dust and other contaminants. The experimental conditions for wear test include: Two different load applications of 1 Kg and 2 Kg for 5 minutes, sliding speed of 1 m/s, 1000 m of sliding distance and performed in normal atmospheric conditions. In this testing method the speed and track radius were kept constant and the wear rate was recorded simultaneously. From the wear test result it was revealed that the sample with 7.5% of GGBS provides the minimum wear rate

comparing to other three compositions. The wear rate values and the coefficient of friction values obtained are represented in the Table 6 and figure 9.

Table 6. Values of wear characteristics obtained from test results

SampleDetails	Wear Rate (Micrometer)		Coefficient of Friction	
	Load (1Kg)	Load (2Kg)	Load (1 Kg)	Load (2 Kg)
Al 6061	98	176	0.45	0.48
Al6061+2.5%ofGGBS	87	153	0.43	0.45
Al6061+5%ofGGBS	64	117	0.41	0.42
Al6061+7.5%ofGGBS	59	105	0.40	0.40

Fig.9 Wear Test Results

The hard GGBS particles which impart higher hardness to the composites can also be attributed for the increased wear-resisting characteristic of the composites as the wear-rate is bound to decrease with the increasing hardness. The reinforced GGBS particles prevent deformation of the matrix by resisting the deformation providing hardness as well as wear-resistance to the aluminium composite. The wear-rate drops with the increase in GGBS reinforcement (Yilmaz, 2001). The maximum enhancement in wear-rate is revealed for 5% GGBS inclusion while the 7.5% inclusion provided comparatively lesser improvement which can be noticed from experimental outcomes. The coefficient of friction is observed to decrease with the rise in GGBS particles and this reveals that the GGBS particles (particularly aluminium oxide and silicon oxide) act as solid lubricants and reduce friction. The micro structural study reveals that GGBS particles are uniformly embedded into the Al6061 matrix for all the reinforced compositions. The lesser

improvement in wear-resistance noted after 5% inclusion may be indicative that optimum reinforcement level is somewhere around 7.5% inclusion or the formation of clusters (at very few locations) at this quantity of reinforcement addition.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The machinability studies carried out on Al6061/GGBS composites have revealed the following inferences.

The mechanical tests showed that the mechanical characteristics enhanced with the increase in GGBS reinforcement. The Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite attained the maximum enhancement in properties. Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite's Brinell hardness improved to 110 BHN, Ultimate Tensile strength improved to 210 MPa and Wear rate (Load 2 Kg.) decreased to 105 micrometer compared to unreinforced Al6061specimen 's values of 64 BHN, 135 MPa and 176 micrometer respectively. Since the Al6061/GGBS composite contains hard and abrasive reinforcement (Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag) particles its ductility has decreased in proportion to the inclusion of GGBS percentage. Al6061/7.5 wt.% GGBS composite's impact strength(Charpy) decreased to 7.9Joule compared to Al6061specimen's 15 J.

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